

The Role of Foreign Direct Investment in the Rise of Emerging Economies

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Abstract

Rising foreign direct investments (FDI) is considered as strong evidence of globalization. FDI plays a very important role in all countries, especially for developing economies, which are considered to be the engine of economic growth and development. The present paper analyses the role of FDI on emerging economies based on reviewing previous research in this domain. The first part of the article presents the characteristics of developed, developing and emerging economies and a characterization of FDI in terms of determinants and benefits. The second part includes a review on previous theories regarding the impact of FDI on economic growth, evaluating the impact of FDI on economic growth in emerging economies and the relationship between FDI and wage level. The main findings show that FDI plays a particularly important role in all the quantitative factors of economic growth and the contribution to economic growth is amplified by the positive interaction with human capital and sound macroeconomic policies and institutional stability. Most studies indicate a beneficial impact of FDI on the growth of host countries and the positive effects of FDI on salaries and job creation. However, some researchers claim that foreign investors tend to discourages wage growth in local firms.

Keywords: Foreign direct investment, FDI, emerging countries, developed countries, developing countries, economic growth.

Introduction

Globalization has become a path to global economic development and growth which makes national isolation no longer a solution, contributing to the understanding of the world as a whole and where the intensity of the effects of globalization is not equal to all, depending on the individual, the way of life, the social level, the education and the cultural nature of each individual (Hirst, Thompson & Bromley, 2015). Based on the literature, the relationship between FDI and globalization was analysed in this paper. FDIs of multinational companies play a significant role in the evolution of the economy as a whole (Narula & Dunning, 2010), in connecting the economy of various countries and through them (Charaia, Chochia & Lashkhi, 2020), multinationals develop international production activities, emphasizing global interstate interdependencies in a process of increasing the integration process (Simionescu, 2018). Thus, the proliferation of FDIs, especially those practiced by multinationals, has had a significant impact on the process of globalization and the dispersal of the activities of these corporations has accentuated interstate interdependencies, integrating them into a complex system of international production (Sarbu, 2015). The growing importance of FDI in the process of globalization is reflected in various economic indicators (Szeles & Saman, 2020).

Investments are the consequence of the company's main financial decision, which involves the creation of production and marketing (Osadchy et al., 2018). The conceptual and meaningful content of FDI has constantly expanded, starting from the multiple forms created by investing firms or from the different sorts of control they have over the companies they invest in, although it has concentrated and unified with the increasingly complex macro-investment processes of the globalized economy (Wang et al., 2021). There are traditions of a phenomenon of concrete multiplication of FDI, in a significant global area, even before the First World War, when over 35% of the wealth of the United Kingdom's economy, as a relevant example, came from outside it (Kuznets, 2019). The described phenomenon has already become established, has been nuanced and delimited in the last two decades of the twentieth century, by conceptualizing FDI, a phenomenon combining organizational features and features of transnational business networks with the emergence and development of transnational corporations (SavoIU, Dinu & Ciuca, 2013).

This initial significance of FDI underscores the various forms of spatial dominance and gradual coverage of international markets, with an emphasis on microeconomic impact. The shift from classical to Keynesian and neoclassical economic theory accentuated the behavior of the economy as a whole (Jackson, 2013), along with the significance of macroeconomics and its aggregates, that transformed FDI into an integrated internationalized business concept and later into a significant issue of economic globalization. Over the last decade, the growth and value of this phenomenon has intensified so rapidly that it has contributed to more than 20% of world GDP (Nistor, 2015). Two and a half decades ago, FDIs were micro-economically conceptualized as ownership of assets by a foreign resident in order to control the use of those assets, and later the phenomenon of conceptual homogenization began to gradually replace diversification and nuance (SavoIU, Dinu & Ciuca, 2013). In low-income economies, FDI and small business development are the two major elements of microeconomic growth, and also FDI, but together with net exports, became the major factors of macroeconomic development (Ciani & Imbruno, 2017; Nițescu, Murgu & Căpriță, 2019). Some of the most important positive elements refer to stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship (Dima, 2021), new business development (Trifu Girneata & Potcovaru, 2015) helping local industry to become more competitive (Dima, 2018; Trifu, Girneata & Potcovaru, 2014).

Literature Review

The countries of the world are divided from the perspective of development, in three categories, respectively: The richest developed countries in the world are post-industrialized economies characterized by high per capita income, competitive industry and a good transport, communications and energy infrastructure. Developing countries are low-income states per capita, characterized by limited industrialization and a stagnant economy (Geleilate et al., 2016). Emerging countries are developing countries that have managed to reach a certain point of industrialization, modernization and accelerated economic growth since the 1980s. The differences between emerging and developing states are nuanced, constantly in fact, in the differences in terms of development and per capita income (Table 1).

Table 1. Differences between developed, emerging and developing economies

Differentiation	Developed economies	Emerging economies	Developing economies
Industry	Very developed	Accelerated improvement	Low
Competition	Low	Moderate, growing tendency	Limited
Trade barriers	Very high	Accelerated liberalization	Moderate to high
Trade volume	High	High	Low
FDI	High	Moderate, growing tendency	Low

Source: Developed by author, based on literature review

Emerging economies are developing markets that, over time, have made progress in relatively accelerating the improvement of living standards. Thus, the substantial improvement of the position on the world market from the economic point of view, has made the emerging markets the main destination of exports, investments and supply for the developed economies. From this context, however, there is an unfavourable aspect for emerging countries, namely that these economies have become a market for the production of developed economies but at the same time their market for supply of raw materials and cheap semi-finished products (Girneata, 2015; Rauch, Dallasega & Matt, 2016).

FDI plays a very important role in all countries, especially for developing economies, which are considered to be the engine of economic growth and development. Foreign capital can help reduce the gap between capital

requirements and national economies, increase the level of qualification in the host economy, improve market access and contribute to technology transfer and good governance (Mukhtorovna, 2021).

Two correlated indicators are used to determine the magnitude of the FDI economic phenomenon, FDI flows and FDI stocks. Foreign direct investment flows (FDI flows) are the amounts of investments made by foreign investors over a period of time (usually one year). Investment flows could be:

- FDI inflows - investments made in a country by non-resident investors of the reporting economy;
- FDI outflows - investments made in another country by resident investors of the reporting economy.

Annually, FDI flows are recorded at net value, respectively by decreasing the debts from capital loans regarding the operations between the direct investor and its foreign subsidiaries. FDI stocks represent the value of the participants in the capital and of the reserves (including the retained profits) pertaining to the investing company to which is added the value of the net debts of the subsidiaries to the investing company. FDI stocks data are presented at book or historical value, that reflect prices at the investment moment (Wacker, 2016). The main characteristics of FDI in terms of definition, determinants and benefits are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Characterization of FDI

Definition	FDI is the long-term investment relationship between a non-resident entity and a resident entity. It usually involves the investor exercising tremendous managerial power in the organization where he has invested.
Determinants	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Framework policies for FDI (trade policy, fiscal and monetary policy, regional development policy);- Determining economic factors (market size, capitalization of resources, efficiency);- Determining business factors (incentives).
Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Increasing capital investments in the economy;- Increasing revenues to the state budget;- Access to modern management;- Development of local human capital by raising the level of skills and knowledge;- Creating a highly competitive environment and boosting the efficiency of local businesses.

Source: Developed by author, based on literature review

Research Methodology

The main objective of this paper is to analyze the role of FDI on emerging economies. The research methodology consists of reviewing and objectively evaluating previous research in this domain. Therefore, various studies were investigated both from the perspective of the authors who support the benefits brought by FDI, as well as from the perspective of the authors who present the negative aspects of FDI in the economy of the host country. The secondary objectives were the following:

- Illustrating the characteristics of developed, developing and emerging economies;
- Analysing the impact of FDI on economic growth in emerging economies;
- Evaluating the relationship between FDI and wage level.

The information in the following section of this article is structured according to the previously stated secondary objectives.

Characteristics of Developed, Developing and Emerging Economies

In the specialized economic literature, a series of characteristics common to developed countries, developing countries and emerging countries, are presented characteristics. These will be briefly summarized below.

Developed countries are very diverse in terms of area, population size, endowment with natural resources, geographical position. Beyond this diversity, however, developed countries have a number of common features such as (Frolova et al., 2018; Johnson, 2021):

- the existence of an economic structure characterized by the predominance of industry and services;
- these countries have moved from the traditional industries (steel, textile, building materials, machine building) to the industries based on information and cutting-edge technology (electronics, computer science, biotechnology, new materials);
- the largest share of the economy is in the tertiary sector (services in the broadest sense) and the secondary sector (the manufacturing industry in which high value-added activities predominate), while the primary sector (which includes those activities related to the exploration and exploitation of raw materials) occupies a small share in the total GDP;
- economic efficiency and labour productivity are much higher due to a real revolution in management that took place in several stages after the Second World War;
- the exports are characterized by great diversity and by the predominance of processed products, with high added value;
- the export of services has a high and increasing share in the case of these countries;
- per capita income is among the highest in the world, so the standard of living of the vast majority of citizens is at the right rates;
- the social and health insurance system is very well developed, which is also reflected in the existence of one of the highest life expectancies in the world;
- these are mostly the countries of origin and destination of foreign direct investment flows.
- most multinational companies have developed countries as the country of origin of the parent company.

As for the main common features specific to the group of **developing countries** (Loayza, Schmidt-Hebbel & Servén, 2000; Schneider & Maxfield, 2018), these are:

- these are mostly countries resulting from the collapse of colonial empires, to which are added the states of South America;
- they hold, in most cases, savings that are predominantly in the primary sector, such as the exploitation of natural resources or the agricultural sector;
- the industrial and service sectors are relatively underdeveloped or, where they exist, unequally distributed within the economy concerned;
- most developing countries have very high levels of debt, classified by the World Bank as severely indebted;
- the population is mainly located in rural areas and access to education, health and information is uneven and relatively low.

From the perspective of the characteristics of **emerging economies**, the most important features of these economies are (Wright et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2020):

- lower level of economic and financial development;
- high degree of exchange rate volatility;
- lack of transparency and weaknesses in legislation (which encourages corruption and unethical practices);

- social stability and tolerance;
- more important profit opportunities than those offered by developed countries;
- stronger cooperation with international financial institutions and higher growth prospects compared to developed economies.

Some of these characteristics (growth prospects, high profit opportunities, social stability and tolerance, closer cooperation with international financial institutions) and at the same time, the improvement of other characteristics (degree of development, transparency, legislative framework) can contribute to the creation of an attractive business environment for foreign investment (direct and portfolio) and last but not least for international exchanges (Table 3).

Table 3. Characteristics of developed, emerging and developing economies

Characteristics	Developed economies	Emerging economies	Developing economies
Education level	High	Medium	Low
Economic and political freedom	Free	Relatively free	Repressed
Economic and political system	Capitalist	Rapid transition to capitalism	Authoritarian, socialist or communist
Regulatory environment	Minimal	Economic liberalization	Very regulated, burdensome
Country risk	Low	Variable	Moderate towards high
Infrastructure	Well developed	Moderate, with a tendency to improve	Inadequate

Source: Developed by author, based on literature review

Theories on the Impact of FDI on Economic Growth

FDI plays a particularly important role in all the quantitative factors of economic growth because the role of investments in the development and economic growth of an economy is significantly complex. Investments influence property structures, economic structures by branches and sub-branches, technological structures, employment structures with both direct and indirect social consequences, stimulating the pace of economic growth. Thus, an important category of investments with an impact on the processes of development and economic growth are the direct foreign ones (Pelinescu & Radulescu, 2009). A study by Agrawal and Khan (2011) on FDI in China and India demonstrate the importance of education in enhancing the impact of FDI on economic growth. Education becomes more effective when associated with foreign knowledge, the interaction between the schooling rate and FDI is significantly positive, suggesting the mutual empowerment between human capital and the foreign knowledge involved in FDI. Makino, Lau and Yeh (2002) consider that the real motive of an investment is a unique asset that gives some advantages over other companies. Berthélemy and Demurger (2000) point out that the contribution of FDI to economic growth is conditioned by the existence of a link between investment flows and technology transfers. For FDI to improve its economic performance, the volume of greenfield investments must exceed that of state-owned control package purchases.

The impact of FDI on economic growth is also related to the level of economic development, the economic and social characteristics of the host country, i.e., indicators such as GDP/capita, level of education, institutional development, economic freedom, which is the economic environment of the country. (Baiashvili & Gattini, 2020). Chakrabarti (2003) developed a theory of the spatial distribution of FDI and the determinants that influence them. Among the main allocation factors, in his FDI theory, the author predicts market size, labour costs, customs costs, exchange rate, and political stability, transportation costs by analogy with the economic and political characteristics of potential rival host economies. Sanchez-Robles and Bengoa (2003) analyze the connection between economic freedom, FDI and economic growth, for a sample including 18 Latin American countries, the analysis period covering the period, 1970-1999. The study results suggest that the host country's

economic freedom is a favorable determinant of FDI inflows and that FDI are strongly associated with host country economic growth. But for host countries to benefit from long-term capital flows, the authors consider that the host country needs adequate human capital, economic stability and liberalized markets. Makki and Somwaru (2004) examine the role of FDI and trade in promoting economic growth in selected developing countries and the interaction between FDI, trade and growth. The results of the study indicate that FDI, trade, human capital and domestic investment are important sources of economic growth for developing countries.

At the same time, FDI's contribution to economic growth is amplified by the positive interaction with human capital and sound macroeconomic policies and institutional stability. Wang (2009) studies the heterogeneous effects of various sector-wide FDI inflows on economic growth in 12 Asian economies. The results show that FDI in the production sector has a significant and positive effect on economic growth in the host economies. Meanwhile, FDI inflows into non-producing sectors do not have an important role in economic growth. Driffield and Jones (2013) examine the relative contributions of FDI, official development assistance, and migrant remittances to economic growth in developing countries. In addition, the authors also analyze the importance of institutions, not only for direct growth, but also for the interactions between institutions and other sources of growth. The results of the analysis show that all sources of foreign capital have a positive and significant impact on growth, when institutions are taken into account. Other authors analyze the effects of remittances and FDI on the volatility of economic growth in the case of Morocco (Bouoiyour, Selmi & Miftah, 2016). The results of the study provide clear evidence that remittances are less volatile than FDI in terms of training duration, intensity and cluster volatility. In addition, remittances can dampen growth volatility, while foreign direct investment flows amplify it.

Estimates of the Impact of FDI on Economic Growth in Emerging Economies

In general, studies on the effects of FDI on the growth of host countries demonstrate their beneficial impact. Pegkas (2015) analyses the relationship between FDI and economic growth and the effects of FDI on economic growth in euro area countries in the period 2002-2012. The paper uses panel data estimates to test the relationship between variables. The results of the study indicate that the stock of FDI is a significant factor that has a positive influence on economic growth in the euro area countries. Another study analyses the contribution of FDI inflows to Malaysian economic growth through an endogenous growth model (Fadhil & Almsafir, 2015). Annual data covers the period 1975 and 2010. The results show that FDI flows, together with the development of human capital, contribute strongly to economic growth. Yao (2006) analyses the effects of exports and FDI on economic performance, using a data set that included 28 Chinese provinces between 1978 and 2000. The results of the study suggest that both exports and FDI have a strong and positive effect on economic growth. Li and Liu (2005) empirically investigate whether FDI influences economic growth in eighty-four countries between 1970 and 1999. In this regard, a significant endogenous relationship between FDI and economic growth has been identified since the mid-1980s in developing countries.

However, there are studies that show that there is no long-term or short-term effect of FDI on economic growth (Herzer, & Klasen, 2008). Another study shows that FDI does not exert an independent influence on economic growth (Carkovic & Levine, 2002). The results of the study are inconsistent with the idea that FDI has a positive impact on economic growth, while the authors argue that the cross-country analysis - corroborated by evidence of a microeconomic nature - reduces confidence that FDI is accelerating GDP growth.

Empirical Studies on the Relationship between FDI and Wage Level

One of the research issues addressing the effects of FDI is the impact of FDI on wage levels. Therefore, there is empirical evidence in the literature that claims that employees in industries with a higher presence of foreign investors enjoy higher wages and higher wage growth (Bedi, & Cielik, 2002). As a result of concerns about the negative impact of the growth of multinational businesses on local employees, some researchers investigate whether FDI benefits local company employees by increasing wages (Tomohara & Takii, 2011). The results show that the activities of foreign enterprises bring an advantage to the employees of local companies, an

increase in their salary level, thus adding to the list of possible benefits brought by FDI and the positive effects of FDI on salaries, among other benefits, such as job creation in the host country, an aspect frequently highlighted in previous research.

Other researchers studied the implications of the activities of multinational enterprises on wages (Saglam & Sayek, 2011). The findings show that an increase in the activities of multinational enterprises influences the increase of average wages in the local economy, while contributing to a greater dispersion of wages between multinational enterprises and local firms. Noria (2015) assesses the relative importance of trade openness and FDI in explaining the inter-industry pay gap for the case of Mexico. The main findings of the study show that trade openness does not have a statistically significant effect on the interindustry wage gap, while for the FDI case, a positive nonlinear relationship is found to exist. Munoz-Bullon and Sanchez-Bueno (2013) examine whether the presence of subsidiaries of multinational companies in the Spanish manufacturing industry affects wages in domestic firms in the same industry. The results of the study show that the impact of the presence of foreign enterprises on domestic salaries is significantly more positive for employees of domestic enterprises but who have a higher level of skills. Other authors point out that only employees in domestic firms with a highly skilled workforce will benefit from wage benefits, as a result of their foreign presence in the industry, and decision-makers should keep in mind that not all FDI will automatically generate collateral benefits for local businesses (Munoz-Bullon & Sanchez-Bueno, 2013). Te Velde and Morrissey (2002) also argue that foreign-owned firms tend to pay higher wages in developing countries, and skilled workers tend to earn higher incomes than less skilled workers.

But on the other hand, there are studies that claim that takeovers by foreign investors of companies tend to have no effect on wages or on the contrary have a negative effect on them. Vijaya and Kaltani (2007) present an empirical investigation of the impact of FDI on wages in the production sector for various economies. The results indicate that the flow of FDI generally has a negative impact on wages in the production sector and the impact is stronger on women's wages. The paper argues that a possible explanation for such an impact may be due to declining bargaining power in labour, due to new labour market arrangements in a global economy, in which capital is free to move between countries in looking for more favourable conditions. Another study by Chen, Ge and Lai (2011) provides micro-evidence of a close link between foreign participation and wage inequality. The results indicate that the presence of foreign investment in Hong Kong, Macao and Taiwan (HMT) has a significant negative impact on the level of pay in local firms, and also discourages wage growth in such firms. In general, the evidence suggests that exposure to foreign investment deepens wage inequalities between domestic enterprises.

In general, previous studies show a number of positive effects of FDI on recipient local economies, in terms of:

- creating a highly competitive environment and boosting the efficiency of local businesses;
- creating new jobs (especially in the case of setting up new companies with foreign capital), thus contributing to improving employment and reducing unemployment;
- the development of local human capital by raising the level of skills and knowledge, this being achieved through training programs for staff employed in multinational companies;
- transfer of technology, know-how and good practices to local businesses;
- the increase of the living standard in the host economy, as a result of the salary level practiced by the multinational companies.

Without claiming that the benefits of FDI recognized in the literature are the only ones, they must be corroborated with a number of negative or less favourable aspects that FDI may have on recipient countries, namely:

- when foreign companies enter the internal market, they can create tensions in the labour market as a result of the mass redundancy of staff in privatized companies, even if compensation is granted for a limited period of time;
- the issue of the ratio between reinvested and repatriated profits;
- environmental problems due to pollution by relocating activities in developed countries;
- reducing the likelihood of survival of local firms, the effects of competition can also have a negative influence, which occurs when multinationals produce at lower costs than local businesses, the latter being forced to reduce their production, which can lead to reduction or cessation the activities of local businesses;
- in the case of the withdrawal of foreign companies, this can have significant negative effects, which would lead to significant imbalances in the local market (for example, they will leave behind job losses and related difficulties);
- FDI determines a certain degree of economic dependence on the economic evolution in the countries of origin of FDI, context in which, a risk can be triggered in the economy of the country, through the effect of contagion.

Comparing the advantages and disadvantages of FDI requires careful analysis, as there may be subtle aspects of some issues that could be overlooked. Consequently, when the focus is on the benefits of FDI, the existence of an unfavourable aspect should not be ruled out.

Conclusions

FDI is a widely debated topic in the economic literature, these being analyzed from different perspectives, which refer to their potential positive or negative effects, in host or home economies, benefits, costs, their contribution to growth economic and development. FDI brings capital, own technology, know - how, senior management, contributes to the increase of revenues to the state budget, generates value - added creative activities and demonstrates excellence in carrying out technological innovation operations. Foreign investment is considered the most efficient and secure way to integrate into the world economy and re-specialize a national economy, and the potential impact has become recognized at the level of companies, authorities, host countries or economists analyzing the FDI phenomenon. Thus, the relationship between FDI and growth is an important topic, frequently addressed over time and today, demonstrating the interest of researchers and economists in understanding the theoretical and practical understanding of the impact of FDI on growth in emerging economies.

References

- i. Agrawal, G., & Khan, M. A. (2011). *Impact of FDI on GDP: A comparative study of China and India. International Journal of Business and Management*, 6(10), 71.
- ii. Baiashvili, T., & Gattini, L. (2020). *Impact of FDI on economic growth: The role of country income levels and institutional strength (No. 2020/02). EIB working papers*.
- iii. Bedi, A. S., & Cielik, A. (2002). *Wages and wage growth in Poland: The role of foreign direct investment. Economics of Transition*, 10(1), 1-27.
- iv. Bengoa, M., & Sanchez-Robles, B. (2003). *Foreign direct investment, economic freedom and growth: new evidence from Latin America. European journal of political economy*, 19(3), 529-545.
- v. Berthélemy, J. C., & Demurger, S. (2000). *Foreign direct investment and economic growth: theory and application to China. Review of development economics*, 4(2), 140-155.
- vi. Bouoiyour, J., Selmi, R., & Miftah, A. (2016). *What mitigates economic growth volatility in Morocco?: Remittances or FDI. Journal of Economic Integration*, 65-102.

- vii. Carkovic, M., & Levine, R. (2002). *Does foreign investment accelerate economic growth*. University of Minn-esota Working Paper.
- viii. Chakrabarti, A. (2003). *A theory of the spatial distribution of foreign direct investment*. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 12(2), 149-169.
- ix. Charaia, V., Chochia, A., & Lashkhi, M. (2020). *The impact of fdi on Economic development: The Case of Georgia*. *TalTech Journal of European Studies*, 10(2), 96-116.
- x. Chen, Z., Ge, Y., & Lai, H. (2011). *Foreign direct investment and wage inequality: Evidence from China*. *World Development*, 39(8), 1322-1332.
- xi. Ciani, A., & Imbruno, M. (2017). *Microeconomic mechanisms behind export spillovers from FDI: evidence from Bulgaria*. *Review of World Economics*, 153(4), 703-734.
- xii. Dima, A. (2021). *The Importance of Innovation in Entrepreneurship for Economic Growth and Development. A Bibliometric Analysis*. *Review of International Comparative Management*, 22(1), 120-131.
- xiii. Dima, A. (2018). *Where is Production Industry heading In the Context of Globalization 2.0*. *In Proceedings of the 31st International Business Information Management Association Conference (IBIMA)*, 1262-1273.
- xiv. Driffield, N., & Jones, C. (2013). *Impact of FDI, ODA and migrant remittances on economic growth in developing countries: A systems approach*. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 25(2), 173-196.
- xv. Fadhil, M. A., & Almsafir, M. K. (2015). *The role of FDI inflows in economic growth in Malaysia (time series: 1975-2010)*. *Procedia economics and finance*, 23, 1558-1566.
- xvi. Frolova, E. E., Zankovsky, S. S., Dudin, M. N., Zinkovsky, S. B., & Kirsanov, A. N. (2018). *Studying concepts of the breakthrough economic reforms in selected developed and developing countries and regions of the world: Economic and legal aspects*. *J. Advanced Res. L. & Econ.*, 9, 1236.
- xvii. Geleilate, J. M. G., Magnusson, P., Parente, R. C., & Alvarado-Vargas, M. J. (2016). *Home country institutional effects on the multinationality–performance relationship: A comparison between emerging and developed market multinationals*. *Journal of International Management*, 22(4), 380-402.
- xviii. Girneata, A. (2015). *The Evolution of the Textile and Clothing Industry–Romania: From Lohn to Loss*. *Revista Economica*, 67(4), 176-187.
- xix. Herzer, D., & Klasen, S. (2008). *In search of FDI-led growth in developing countries: The way forward*. *Economic Modelling*, 25(5), 793-810.
- xx. Hirst, P., Thompson, G., & Bromley, S. (2015). *Globalization in question*. John Wiley & Sons.
- xxi. Jackson, W. A. (2013). *The desocialising of economic theory*. *International Journal of Social Economics*.
- xxii. Johnson, H. G. (2021). *Economic policies towards less developed countries (Vol. 1)*. Routledge.
- xxiii. Kuznets, S. (2019). *Economic growth and income inequality*. *In The gap between rich and poor (pp. 25-37)*. Routledge.
- xxiv. Li, X., & Liu, X. (2005). *Foreign direct investment and economic growth: an increasingly endogenous relationship*. *World development*, 33(3), 393-407.
- xxv. Liu, W., Liu, R. H., Chen, H., & Mboga, J. (2020). *Perspectives on disruptive technology and innovation: Exploring conflicts, characteristics in emerging economies*. *International Journal of Conflict Management*.
- xxvi. Loayza, N., Schmidt-Hebbel, K., & Servén, L. (2000). *Saving in developing countries: an overview*. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 14(3), 393-414.
- xxvii. Makino, S., Lau, C. M., & Yeh, R. S. (2002). *Asset-exploitation versus asset-seeking: Implications for location choice of foreign direct investment from newly industrialized economies*. *Journal of international business studies*, 33(3), 403-421.

- xxviii. Makki, S. S., & Somwaru, A. (2004). *Impact of foreign direct investment and trade on economic growth: Evidence from developing countries*. *American journal of agricultural economics*, 86(3), 795-801.
- xxix. Mukhtorovna, N. D. (2021). *Importance of foreign investments in the development of the digital economy*. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 219-224.
- xxx. Muñoz-Bullón, F., & Sánchez-Bueno, M. J. (2013). *Multinational enterprises and domestic wages: The contingent effect of skill composition*. *International Business Review*, 22(6), 918-931.
- xxxi. Narula, R., & Dunning, J. H. (2010). *Multinational enterprises, development and globalization: Some clarifications and a research agenda*. *Oxford Development Studies*, 38(3), 263-287.
- xxxii. Nistor, P. (2015). *FDI implications on BRICS economy growth*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 32, 981-985.
- xxxiii. Nițescu, D. C., Murgu, V., & Căpriță, E. D. (2019). *Impact of labor, FDI and R&D on business sustainability*. *Amfiteatru. Economic*, 21, 795-815.
- xxxiv. Noria, G. L. (2015). *The effect of trade and FDI on inter-industry wage differentials: The case of Mexico*. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 34, 381-397.
- xxxv. Osadchy, E. A., Akhmetshin, E. M., Amirova, E. F., Bochkareva, T. N., Gazizyanova, Y., & Yumashev, A. V. (2018). *Financial statements of a company as an information base for decision-making in a transforming economy*.
- xxxvi. Pegkas, P. (2015). *The impact of FDI on economic growth in Eurozone countries*. *The Journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 12(2), 124-132.
- xxxvii. Pelinescu, E., & Radulescu, M. (2009). *The impact of foreign direct investment on the economic growth and countries' export potential*. *Romanian Journal of Economic Forecasting*, 4(1), 153-169.
- xxxviii. Rauch, E., Dallasega, P., & Matt, D. T. (2016). *Sustainable production in emerging markets through Distributed Manufacturing Systems (DMS)*. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 127-138.
- xxxix. Saglam, B. B., & Sayek, S. (2011). *MNEs and wages: the role of productivity spillovers and imperfect labor markets*. *Economic Modelling*, 28(6), 2736-2742.
- xl. Savoiu, G., Dinu, V. & Ciuca, S. (2013). *Foreign Direct Investment based on Country Risk and other Macroeconomic Factors. Econometric Models for Romanian Economy*. *Journal for Economic Forecasting, Institute for Economic Forecasting*, vol. 0(1), pages 39-61, March.
- xli. Sarbu, M. R. (2015). *Globalization and foreign direct investments*. *CES Working Papers*, 7(2), 324-331.
- xlii. Schneider, B. R., & Maxfield, S. (2018). *Performance in Developing Countries*. *Business and the state in developing countries*, 3.
- xliii. Simionescu, M. (2018). *Effects of European economic integration on foreign direct investment: The case of Romania*. *Economics and Sociology*, 11(4), 96-105.
- xliv. Szeles, M. R., & Saman, C. (2020). *Globalisation economic growth and covid-19. Insights from international finance*. *Romanian Journal Of Economic Forecasting*, 23(3), 78.
- xlv. te Velde, D. W., & Morrissey, O. (2002). *Foreign direct investment: Who gains*. *ODI Briefing Paper*, 2020-01.
- xlvi. Tomohara, A., & Takii, S. (2011). *Does globalization benefit developing countries? Effects of FDI on local wages*. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 33(3), 511-521.
- xlvii. Trifu, A. E., Girneata, A., & Potcovaru, M. (2014). *Influence of natural factors upon the organization activities*. *Revista de Management Comparat International*, 15(4), 487.
- xlviii. Trifu, A. E., Gîrneată, A., & Potcovaru, A. M. (2015). *The Impact of Regulations upon the Startup of New Businesses*. *Economia: Seria Management*, 18, 49-59.
- xlix. Vijaya, R. M., & Kaltani, L. (2007). *Foreign direct investment and wages: a bargaining power approach*. *Journal of World-Systems Research*, 83-95.
- l. Wacker, K. M. (2016). *(When) should we use foreign direct investment data to measure the activities of multinational corporations? Theory and evidence*. *Review of International Economics*, 24(5), 980-999.

- li. Wang, M. (2009). *Manufacturing FDI and economic growth: evidence from Asian economies*. *Applied Economics*, 41(8), 991-1002.
- lii. Wang, X., Xu, Z., Qin, Y., & Skare, M. (2021). *Foreign direct investment and economic growth: a dynamic study of measurement approaches and results*. *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 1-24.
- liii. Wright, M., Filatotchev, I., Hoskisson, R. E., & Peng, M. W. (2005). *Strategy research in emerging economies: Challenging the conventional wisdom*. *Journal of management studies*, 42(1), 1-33.
- liv. Yao, S. (2006). *On economic growth, FDI and exports in China*. *Applied Economics*, 38(3), 339-351.